

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF UNILATERAL VS BILATERAL SPINAL ANAESTHESIA USING HYPERBARIC BUPIVACAINE WITH BUPRENORPHINE IN UNILATERAL INGUINAL HERNIA SURGERY

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Abstract

Unilateral spinal anaesthesia can be used for inguinal hernia surgery. The advantage is that it provides a stronger block on the side of surgery and accelerated recovery of the nerve block, with better maintenance of cardiovascular stability. Hence it can be a valuable technique for high-risk patients.

The aim: This randomized controlled trial was designed to evaluate the onset and duration of Sensory and motor block in both unilateral and bilateral spinal anaesthesia and the adverse effects of buprenorphine given intrathecally with 0.5 % bupivacaine for Spinal anaesthesia in patients scheduled for unilateral inguinal hernia surgery.

Materials and methods: it is a comparative two group randomized clinical study with 60 patients with 30 patients in Group U (UNILATERAL) and 30 patients in Group B (BILATERAL) is undertaken to study the changes in haemodynamics and side effects. Whereas, within the group (for the unilateral group) comparison of the time taken to reach L1, T12, T10 and the Bromage time between the surgical side and non-surgical side sides of surgery was done.

Results: T10–T12 spinal anaesthesia was achieved in both groups; the average time to anaesthetic onset in the unilateral group was 5.27 ± 1.2 min, and in the bilateral, it was 5.90 ± 1.02 min (p -value = 0.32). Sensory and motor block lasted longer in the bilateral group when compared to the unilateral group; the incidence of side effects was limited to the occurrence of hypotension and bradycardia in the unilateral group than in the bilateral group. The success rate of unilateral spinal anaesthesia in our study was 100 %.

Conclusion: Because of haemodynamic stability and faster recovery characteristics of unilateral spinal block, it can be used as a suitable technique in patients with a limited cardiovascular reserve and for outpatient anaesthesia.

Keywords: Unilateral spinal anaesthesia, haemodynamic stability, Surgical side and non-surgical sides.

DOI: 10.21303/2504-5679.2023.002783

1. Introduction

Regional anaesthesia is a safe, effective and economical technique for pain relief with the added advantage of the extension of long post-operative analgesia. In addition, surgical repair of inguinal hernia can be performed under regional anaesthesia, general anaesthesia, nerve blocks.

In recent years, the usage of intrathecal adjuvants has gained much popularity with the benefit of prolonging the duration of the blockade, better success rate, patient satisfaction, decreased resource utilization compared with general anaesthesia and faster recovery. Adequate pain management accelerates functional recovery, facilitates rehabilitation and enables the patients to return to their normal activity quickly. Furthermore, the quality of spinal anaesthesia has been reported to be improved by the addition of opioids and other drugs [such as vasoconstrictors, clonidine, neostigmine, ketamine and midazolam] [1, 2].

Unilateral spinal anaesthesia has found a resurgence in recent years. Conventional bilateral spinal anaesthesia is performed in most cases of inguinal hernia repair however unilateral spinal anaesthesia can be used. The basic objective of unilateral spinal anaesthesia is to limit the nerve block exclusively to the surgery site. So important factors affecting successful unilateral subarachnoid block include baricity and volume of drug, the position of the patient, type of needle and its bevel direction and speed of injection [3–5].

The advantage of unilateral spinal anaesthesia over bilateral spinal anaesthesia is that it provides a stronger block on the side of surgery and accelerated recovery of the nerve block. There is a lower incidence of hypotension and better maintenance of cardiovascular stability. Hence it can be a valuable technique for high-risk patients.

The aim of the research: This randomized controlled trial was designed to evaluate the onset and duration of Sensory and motor block in both unilateral and bilateral spinal anaesthesia.

2. Material and methods

Patients who fulfil the inclusion criteria undergo elective inguinal hernia surgeries in Osmania General Hospital, Afzalgunj, Hyderabad.

Inclusion criteria: patients aged between 18 – 65 years belonging to ASA class I & II without any co-morbid disease, admitted for elective inguinal hernia surgeries and patients who have given consent.

Exclusion criteria: patients with co-morbid conditions like diabetes mellitus, asthma, hypertension, cardiac disease, haematological disease allergy to local anaesthetics and patients having absolute contraindication for spinal anaesthesia like raised intracranial pressure, severe hypovolaemia, bleeding diathesis and local infection.

After approval from the ethical committee of our hospital, 60 ASA I and II patients scheduled for elective inguinal hernia surgeries under spinal anaesthesia were chosen for the study.

After approval from the ethical committee of Osmania Medical college, dated – 8/5/2019, registration number – 19102001019D, 60 ASA I and II patients scheduled for elective inguinal hernia surgeries under spinal anaesthesia were chosen for the study.

Patients were allocated to either group unilateral (U) or group (B) bilateral by computer generated randomization table.

A pre-anaesthetic check-up was done one day prior to the surgery. Patients were evaluated for any systemic diseases and laboratory investigations were recorded. The procedure of SAB was explained to the patients, and written consent was obtained. The patients were educated about the use of a visual analogue scale. The preparation of patients included a period of overnight fasting. Patients were premedicated with Tab.Rantac 150 mg and Tab. Alprazolam 0.5 mg H.S.

Boyle's anaesthesia machine was checked. Appropriate endotracheal tubes, working laryngoscope with medium and large size blades, stylet and working suction apparatus were kept ready before the procedure. Emergency drug trays of atropine, adrenaline, mephenteramine, ephedrine, and dopamine were kept ready.

Sample size calculation

The sample size was estimated using the effect size between the unilateral and bilateral hyperbaric buprenorphine for mean Bromage time from the pilot study.⁵ The formula used was:

$$n_i = 2(Z_{1-\alpha/2} + Z_{1-\beta}/ES)^2,$$

where, n_i = sample size required in each of the two groups; $Z_{1-\alpha/2}$ = value from the standard normal distribution holding $1-\alpha/2$ below it = 1.96 for 95 % CI; $Z_{1-\beta}$ = value from the standard normal distribution holding $1-\beta$ below it = 0.84; ES = effect size, for which difference in Bromage time between unilateral and bilateral blocks was considered = 5.57 ± 1.35 min, 6.47 ± 1.21 min.

ES was calculated using formula = (Difference in mean values)/(pooled standard deviation) Substituting the above values in the formula:

$$n_i = 2 [(1.96+0.84)/(0.9/1.25)]^2 = 2 (3.8)^2 = 2 (14.4) = 29.$$

We rounded off the sample size to 30 per group and thus obtained a total sample of 60 patients for the study to have a power of 80 % and 95 % confidence intervals.

Procedure:

Patients were shifted to the OR table, and base vitals were recorded. IV access was obtained on the forearm with No 18G IV cannula, and all patients were preloaded with 10 ml/kg, Ringer's Lactate, 4 ml/kg/hr intra-operatively 15 mins before the surgery. Patients were randomly allocated into groups.

Group U: Hyperbaric bupivacaine 0.5 % (12.5 mg) +90 mcg buprenorphine in lateral position operative side downwards given intrathecally.

Group B: Hyperbaric bupivacaine 0.5 % (12.5 mg) +90 mcg buprenorphine in a sitting position given intrathecally

Under strict asepsis, a lumbar puncture was performed using a 25 G Quincke spinal needle at L3-L4 space. Inj. Bupivacaine 0.5 % hyperbaric 12.5 mg+ Inj Buprenorphine 90 mcg was given over 15 seconds, using a 5cc syringe, by guiding the tip of the spinal needle to the side to be operated on group U and cephalic in group B.

Only after confirming for clear and free flow of CSF drug was injected. Patients were kept in a lateral position for 10min for group U & made supine immediately on the OT table for group B, with a 10-degree head-down tilt of the table. The surgeon was allowed to start the procedure when the block level reached T8 sensory dermatome. Intraoperatively pulse rate, non-invasive blood pressure, electrocardiogram, and SpO₂ were recorded, and all assessments were performed on both sides every 2 minutes for the first 10 minutes, every 10 minutes for the next 50 minutes and every 15 minutes till the end of surgery.

The time of onset of L1, T12, and T10 sensory block and peak sensory block was noted using the pinprick method, and the time of onset of Bromage 3 motor block was noted.

Motor block was assessed with the Modified Bromage scale

Bromage 1 – the patient is unable to move the hip but is able to move the knee and ankle
Bromage 2 – the patient is unable to move the hip and knee but able to move the ankle
Bromage 3 – the patient is unable to move the hip, knee and ankle.

The following parameters were recorded.

Hypotension (>20 % fall of baseline blood pressure) was treated with a bolus dose of 6 mg mephentermine i.v. Bradycardia (pulse rate < 50 bpm) was treated with 0.6 mg atropine.iv

Incidence of respiratory depression, defined as respiratory rate less than 9/min and SpO₂ less than 90 % on room air, was noted. Side effects, if any, were noted.

Post-operatively, regression of the sensory block and the motor blockade to reach modified Bromage 0 was noted. The pain was assessed using the «Visual Analogue Scale» advocated by Re-vill and Robinson in 1976. It is a linear scale consisting of a 10 cm line anchored at one end. Visual analogue scale by a label such as «No pain» and the other end with «Worst pain imaginable». The patient simply marks the line to indicate the pain intensity. Supplemental analgesia was given for a visual analogue score of more than 6. The time of supplemental analgesia was noted.

A visual analogue scale was used to assess post-operative pain. 0 = no pain, 10 = severe pain.

Statistical Methods: Descriptive statistics have been carried out in the present study. Results on continuous measurements are presented on Mean ± SD (Min-Max), and results on categorical measurements are presented in number (%). Significance is assessed at a 5 % level of significance.

The following assumptions on data are that dependent variables should be normally distributed, samples drawn from the population should be random, and cases of the samples should be independent.

Statistical analysis was done by applying the continuous and categorical data represented as means and percentages/proportions, respectively. The comparison of continuous and ordinal variables between the two groups – unilateral and bilateral, was made using independent samples t-test and Mann-Whitney U test; whereas, within the group (for the unilateral group) comparison of the time taken to reach L1, T12, T10 and the Bromage time between Surgical side and non-Surgical side sides of surgery was done using paired sample t-test. A $p > 0.05$ is not significant, $p < 0.05$ is significant, $p < 0.001$ is highly significant.

3. Results

All demographic details are insignificant when compared. The time taken to reach L1 was significantly lesser in the patients belonging to the unilateral group. The time taken to reach T10 was significantly lesser in the patients belonging to the unilateral group (**Table 1**).

Table 1

Comparison of basic between the two groups using unpaired t-test

Group	Mean	Std deviation	t-statistic (p-value)	Sig/NS
Age in years				
Unilateral	45.62	10.742	-1.736 (.088)	NS
Bilateral	50.10	9.030		
Weight (in kg)				
Unilateral	66.27	8.250	1.671 (.100)	NS
Bilateral	63.23	5.544		
pre-operative heart rate				
Unilateral	84.67	13.366	.153 (.879)	NS
Bilateral	84.13	13.559		
pre-operative systolic BP				
Unilateral	128.83	11.609	1.158 (.252)	NS
Bilateral	125.50	10.667		
pre-operative diastolic BP				
Unilateral	81.60	8.544	1.081 (.284)	NS
Bilateral	79.33	7.680		
Time is taken (in min) to reach L1				
Unilateral	2.43	0.817	-2.909 (0.005)	Sig
Bilateral	3.07	0.868		
Time is taken (in min) to reach T12				
Unilateral	3.97	1.351	-1.819 (0.074)	NS
Bilateral	4.53	1.042		
Time is taken (in min) to reach T10				
Unilateral	5.27	1.202	-2.193 (0.032)	Sig
Bilateral	5.90	1.029		
Duration of surgery				
Unilateral	90.53	12.233	1.277 (0.207)	NS
Bilateral	86.63	11.418		

The mean heart rate was significantly greater in the bilateral group patients at 10, 15, and 20 minutes post-operatively, whereas at 60 and 120 minutes, it was significantly greater within the unilateral group. However, at all-time points, the heart rate in both groups was within normal limits (**Table 2**).

At 5 min post-operatively, systolic BP was significantly greater in the unilateral group but similar to the bilateral group at all other time points of measurement (**Table 3**).

The diastolic BP was similar in both groups at all measurement time points (**Table 4**).

Table 2

Heart rate (HR) at different post-operative time intervals between the two groups

Time	Group	Mean	Std deviation	t-statistic (p-value)	Sig/NS
HR5MIN	Unilateral	75.83	12.242	-1.890 (.064)	NS
	Bilateral	82.20	13.805		
HR10MIN	Unilateral	73.63	9.242	-2.890 (.005)	Sig
	Bilateral	82.90	14.933		
HR15MIN	Unilateral	74.17	8.987	-2.894 (.005)	Sig
	Bilateral	83.17	14.468		
HR20MIN	Unilateral	73.83	10.570	-2.141 (.036)	Sig
	Bilateral	80.73	14.137		
HR30MIN	Unilateral	74.30	11.665	-1.182 (.242)	NS
	Bilateral	77.83	11.498		
HR45MIN	Unilateral	74.87	12.082	-.308 (.759)	NS
	Bilateral	75.83	12.242		
HR60MIN	Unilateral	82.20	13.805	2.189 (.033)	Sig
	Bilateral	74.87	12.082		
HR90MIN	Unilateral	77.83	11.498	1.182 (.242)	NS
	Bilateral	74.30	11.665		
HR120MIN	Unilateral	80.73	14.137	2.141 (.036)	Sig
	Bilateral	73.83	10.570		

Table 3

Comparison of systolic BP (SBP) at different post-operative time intervals between the two groups

Time	Group	Mean	Std deviation	t-statistic (p-value)	Sig/NS
SBP5	Unilateral	114.63	11.137	15.730 (.000)	Sig
	Bilateral	73.83	8.820		
SBP10	Unilateral	114.63	11.137	.444 (.658)	NS
	Bilateral	113.17	14.235		
SBP15	Unilateral	111.30	10.882	.000 (1.000)	NS
	Bilateral	110.42	9.620		
SBP20	Unilateral	110.23	11.602	.000 (1.000)	NS
	Bilateral	107.10	11.721		
SBP30	Unilateral	110.03	10.588	.000 (1.000)	NS
	Bilateral	108.23	11.532		
SBP45	Unilateral	109.60	10.900	.000 (1.000)	NS
	Bilateral	105.43	10.847		
SBP60	Unilateral	108.30	10.803	.000 (1.000)	NS
	Bilateral	104.23	8.968		
SBP60	Unilateral	108.30	10.803	.000 (1.000)	NS
	Bilateral	104.23	8.968		
SBP90	Unilateral	107.07	9.784	.000 (1.000)	NS
	Bilateral	104.50	9.826		
SBP120	Unilateral	105.77	9.376	.000 (1.000)	NS

Table 4

Comparison of diastolic BP (DBP) at different post-operative time intervals between the two groups

Time	Group	Mean	Std deviation	t-statistic (p-value)	Sig/NS
DBP5	Unilateral	75.90	9.211	.000 (1.000)	NS
	Bilateral	74.93	8.121		
DBP10	Unilateral	71.57	9.489	.000 (1.000)	NS
	Bilateral	68.73	7.241		
DBP15	Unilateral	70.30	9.177	.000 (1.000)	NS
	Bilateral	68.84	8.459		
DBP20	Unilateral	67.37	10.277	.000 (1.000)	NS
	Bilateral	63.72	10.124		
DBP30	Unilateral	66.87	9.944	.000 (1.000)	NS
	Bilateral	64.68	10.265		
DBP45	Unilateral	65.43	10.064	.000 (1.000)	NS
	Bilateral	63.76	9.635		
DBP60	Unilateral	64.67	9.463	.000 (1.000)	NS
	Bilateral	63.94	9.421		
DBP90	Unilateral	65.07	9.417	.000 (1.000)	NS
	Bilateral	63.86	9.470		
DBP120	Unilateral	64.47	9.273	.000 (1.000)	NS
	Bilateral	62.45	8.345		

The heart rate was similar in both groups at all time points of measurement (**Table 5**).

The mean Bromage time between the two groups is significant (**Fig. 1**).

Table 5

Comparison of respiratory rate and oxygen saturation between the two groups using unpaired t-test

Respiratory rate	Mean	Std deviation	t-statistic (p-value)	Sig/NS
Unilateral	15.67	1.605	-1.254 (.215)	NS
Bilateral	16.20	1.690		
SpO ₂				
Unilateral	97.93	.785	0.000 (1.000)	NS
Bilateral	97.02	.740		

Fig. 1. Comparison of mean Bromage time between the two groups using unpaired t-test

The median VAS score at 2 hrs was significantly greater for the patients within the unilateral group. The median VAS score at 4 hrs was significantly greater for the patients within the

unilateral group. Finally, the median VAS score at 6 hrs was significantly greater for the patients within the unilateral group (**Table 6**).

All demographic details are insignificant when compared (**Table 7**).

Table 6

Comparison of VAS score at 2, 4 and 6 hrs between the two groups

Mean Bromage time	Mean	t-statistic (p-value)	Sig/NS
VAS score at 2 hrs			
Unilateral	3	-7.244 (<0.001)	Sig
Bilateral	0		
VAS score at 4 hrs			
Unilateral	6	-6.389 (<0.01)	Sig
Bilateral	3		
VAS score at 6 hrs			
Unilateral	7	-6.107 (<0.01)	Sig
Bilateral	5.5		

Table 7

Distribution of patients in various categories within the two groups

	Unilateral		Bilateral	
	N	%	N	%
ASA grade				
I	18	60.0	17	56.7
II	12	40.0	13	43.3
Side				
Left	15	50.0	11	36.7
Right	15	50.0	19	63.3
The level attained on the surgical side				
T4	0	0	7	23.3
T6	24	80.0	20	66.7
T8	6	20.0	3	10.0
The level attained on the non-surgical side				
T4	0	0	7	23.3
T6	17	56.7	20	66.7
T8	13	43.3	3	10.0
Dose of injection Mepentermine				
6 mg	5	16.7	6	20
nil	25	83.3	24	80
Dose of injection Atropine				
0.6 mg	1	3.3	3	10
nil	29	96.7	27	90

Complications are significant when compared to unilateral and bilateral spinal anaesthesia (**Table 8**).

VAS score is significant compared to unilateral and bilateral spinal anaesthesia (**Table 9**).

Table 8

Distribution of patients according to complications within the two groups

Complications	Unilateral		Bilateral	
	N	%	N	%
Bradycardia	1	3.3	2	6.7
hypotension	3	10	5	16.6

Table 9

Distribution of patients according to VAS scores at 2, 4, 6 hrs within the two groups

	Unilateral		Bilateral	
	N	%	N	%
VAS scores at 2 hrs				
0	0	0	30	100
3	16	53.3	0	0
4	14	46.7	0	0
VAS scores at 4 hrs				
3	1	3.3	16	53.3
4	1	3.3	14	46.7
5	8	26.7	0	0
6	12	40.0	0	0
7	8	26.7	0	0
VAS scores at 6 hrs				
5	0	0	15	50.0
6	7	23.3	15	50.0
7	10	33.3	0	0
8	10	33.3	0	0
9	3	10.0	0	0

The time to reach L1 was significantly greater on the non-surgical side. The time to reach T12 was significantly greater on the non-surgical side. The time to reach T10 was significantly greater on the non-surgical side.

The Bromage time was significantly greater on the non-Surgical side (Table 10).

Table 10

Comparison of time to reach levels between the two sides using paired t-test

	Mean	Std deviation	t-statistic (p-value)	Sig/NS
Time to reach L1				
Surgical side	2.43	.817	-13.857 (<0.001)	Sig
Non-Surgical side	3.60	.894		
Time to reach T12				
Surgical side	3.97	1.351	-5.066 (<0.001)	Sig
Non-Surgical side	4.83	.950		
Time to reach T10 between				
Surgical side	5.27	1.202	-6.618 (<0.001)	Sig
Non-Surgical side	6.53	1.167		
The Bromage time between the two sides				
Surgical side	5.57	1.406	-3.340 (0.002)	Sig
Non-Surgical side	5.90			

4. Discussion

Bilateral SAB is associated with a higher incidence of hemodynamic instability and prolonged post-op stay. Unilateral SAB provides relative hemodynamic stability, rapid return of motor function, and extremely low incidence of urinary retention, and patients are usually eligible for home discharge sooner. So, it could be a better alternative to bilateral spinal anaesthesia [6].

Maintenance of the lateral decubitus position for a determined length is seen to restrict the surgical block to the side to be operated. However, it is difficult to define the exact time for which the patient is to be kept in a lateral position. The literature says 10–20 min time is adequate to achieve unilaterality [7]. In our study, we kept patients in a lateral position for 10 minutes in the U/L group after giving the spinal injection and using the hyperbaric anaesthetic results in a more predictable nerve block than the hypobaric solution. So, we used a hyperbaric solution for our study.

In our study, the mean heart rate was significantly higher in Group U. Studies found results similar to ours [8]. They found a significant difference in the incidence of bradycardia between the groups in favour of the unilateral group. A greater fall in heart rate in the bilateral group could result due to local anaesthetic-related sympathetic blockade. The bradycardia was related to higher sympathetic blockade associated with bilateral spinal anaesthesia in our study. Prevention rather than treatment of haemodynamic disturbances is emphasized in patients undergoing spinal anaesthesia. Prophylactic measures include pre-hydration with intravenous fluids. We gave lactated ringer's solution 10 ml/kg for preloading. Subsequently, 4 ml/kg intraoperative fluid replacement was done, considering the hernia as intermediate fluid loss surgery. A potential means for hypotension prophylaxis is by manipulation of spinal anaesthesia to achieve a predominantly unilateral block. The systolic diastolic pressures were significantly higher in the case of unilateral anaesthesia patients. Our results align with those of Nauman Akhtar et al. [8]. They compared unilateral versus bilateral spinal anaesthesia with respect to haemodynamic changes.

Patients were kept in a lateral position for 10 minutes in the unilateral group. From 1 minute till unilateral recovery group showed higher systolic BP, diastolic BP and meant arterial pressures which was statistically significant.

The number of doses of Mephentermine required was significantly higher in Group B. Similar results were reported [9] who conducted a prospective randomized study in one hundred ASA I–II patients between the age group 18- and 65-years undergoing knee arthroscopy to compare unilateral and conventional bilateral spinal block to evaluate the efficacy and latency of surgical block.

Vaso-pressor was required in the bilateral group. The degree of the sympathetic blockade in spinal anaesthesia is related to the height of sensory anaesthesia. Often the level of the sympathetic blockade is several spinal segments higher since the pre-ganglionic sympathetic fibres are more sensitive to low concentrations of local anaesthetics.

The most important effects of the sympathetic blockade during spinal anaesthesia are on the cardiovascular system causing decreased stroke volume and heart rate [8]. An exclusively unilateral block affects the sensory, motor and sympathetic functions on the operative side and provides an advantage over the bilateral spinal block [10]. So it is important to study the quality and duration of sensory and motor blocks to correlate with haemodynamic data correctly.

We have found a significant difference in the onset of sensory and motor blocks between the groups. Studies reported faster onset of sensory block in the unilateral group. The difference was statistically significant [11].

In our study, the unilateral group showed adequate block on the operative side compared to a higher level of block in the bilateral group. Similar results were reported [12]. Thus, as the level of sympathetic block ascends, the actions of the parasympathetic nervous system are increasingly dominant, and the compensatory mechanisms of the unblocked sympathetic nervous system are diminished. So higher the sympathetic blockade, the more chances of bradycardia and hypotension are there [13].

The drug's degree of caudad or cephalad spread in the sub-arachnoid block depends on the interplay between density and patient position. The distance between left and right nerve roots in the lumbar and thoracic regions is about 10–15 cm, which makes it possible to achieve unilateral

spinal anaesthesia. Only a couple of studies have compared peak sensory levels achieved on operative and non-operative sides in a unilateral group of patients [14, 15]. They found significantly higher sensory levels and more intense motor blocks in the operative limb.

In our study, in the unilateral group, we have got a more intense block on the operative side of the surgery and in group U on the operative side, the highest motor Bromage score was 3 in all the patient's recovery from spinal anaesthesia, depends primarily on the local anaesthetic usage. For ambulatory surgery, the length of hospital stay will depend on the dose and type of anaesthetic used [16]. Our unilateral study group showed a shorter duration of sensory and motor block, although the block lasted for an adequate duration for inguinal hernia surgery. Studies showed no opioid-associated side effects like pruritis, respiratory depression and vomiting due to the usage of buprenorphine in our study [17, 18].

Limitations of the study: The limitation of this study is the small size of the sample considered; since being the first testing phase, further studies are needed.

Prospects for further research: Though none of our patients as well as surgeons, reported any discomfort during surgery, we have not looked for surgeon and patient satisfaction data. We have not looked for and assessed intermediate and long-term side effects of spinal anaesthesia between the groups.

5. Conclusion

From our study, we found that the unilateral spinal anaesthesia group had a lower incidence of hemodynamic changes with respect to bradycardia and hypotension and lower requirement of Mephentermine and Atropine as compared to bilateral adopting a unilateral spinal block producing minimal hemodynamic fluctuations would be beneficial. Unilateral spinal anaesthesia resulted in a lower peak sensory level on the operative side, a similar grade of the motor block on the operative side and faster regression of sensory and motor blocks with no immediate side effects. However, postoperative analgesia time was significantly prolonged in bilateral spinal anaesthesia. So because of haemodynamic stability and faster recovery characteristics of unilateral spinal block, it can be used as a suitable technique in patients with a limited cardiovascular reserve and for outpatient anaesthesia.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in relation to this paper, as well as the published research results, including the financial aspects of conducting the research, obtaining and using its results, as well as any non-financial personal relationships.

Funding

The study was performed without financial support.

Data availability

Data will be made available on reasonable request.

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Received date 14.12.2022

Accepted date 19.01.2023

Published date 31.01.2023

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How to cite: Suman, G., Priyadarshini, N. A., Sravya, T. (2023). A comparative study of unilateral vs bilateral spinal anaesthesia using hyperbaric bupivacaine with buprenorphine in unilateral inguinal hernia surgery. *EUREKA: Health Sciences*, 1, 23–33. doi: <http://doi.org/10.21303/2504-5679.2023.002783>